

Modeling and management knowledge in health surveillance

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Abstract

The phenomenon of individual and collective health in productive organizations, is presented as the combination of a number of particular characteristics of the Organization and production, in which make part of this, computers, tools, skills management, internal professional mobility, the management of the working environment, the professional requirements of development of specific gestures. All these elements are interconnected in the execution of a specific task and according to the nature of each one of them can amplify or minimize the activation of a health problem.

The structure of production adopted by companies, can be characterized as a matrix network, which consists of production of autonomous nodes but inter related through mutual services linked to the needs of each node. Frequently, "the matrix structure is an efficient means to meet the various specialized skills required to solve a complex problem." In this form of interaction is important to analyze, since this autonomy is linked to the work strategies adopted at each node in terms of allocation of tasks, collective management of the work, as well as the implications for the individual management of margins of operation and recovery workers.

This study adopts the perspective of prospective surveillance of activators of a disease as a knowledge management tool, this strategy is based on monitoring and analysis of the reality of work, allowing it to accumulate and structure a precise knowledge about the situations of work on each node. This analysis includes the identification of modifications of the system of work, which can also contribute to increasing exposure to generators of health events.

Our hypothesis considers that these situations of work, the actual surveillance systems are unable to identify the modifications adopted by the workers and they don't granting the possibility of developing tailored preventive actions. Our model was tested in a company with matrix model of production.